

Effect of Socioeconomic Characteristics of Youth Farmers on the Rice Production Project in Ishielu Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria

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The research focused on the effect of socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers on the Rice Production Project in Ishielu local government area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Cluster purposive and random sampling techniques were employed in selecting 120 respondents. Data were collected from the respondents using a close-ended questionnaire. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result showed that about 43.3 percent of the participants were youths. The result further indicates that most of the participants (65.8%) were male with an average household size of 7. The Wald test result showed that the covariate and categorical variables that have significant effect on the dependent variable were; age, non-farm income, household size, marital status (single), educational

qualification (primary and secondary) and primary occupation (farming, civil and public services). The pseudo R^2 of Nagelkerke is 0.822, while the test of hypothesis showed that the chi-square statistics (352.902) is significant at 1% level of significance. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the government should employ the use of improved technology, machines and machineries should be used in the rice production project activities in the study area. This will encourage the young age youth who are graduates to option into the project actively.

Keywords: Youth farmers, socioeconomic characteristics, Ebonyi State rice project, ordinal regression

INTRODUCTION

Rice is the world's most basic food. Rice will continue to be a staple food in the coming decades, be it in terms of food security, poverty alleviation, youth employment, use of scarce resources, or impact on the climate (International Rice Research Institute, 2016). In Nigeria today, rice is ranked first because it has moved from a mere ceremonial to a staple food in most homes as it accounts for about 40% of the total diets of the country's population (Ojogho and Erhabor, 2011 and Selbut, 2003). However, in Nigeria rice which is grown on 1.77 million ha ranks sixth after sorghum (4.0 million ha), millet (3.5 million ha), cowpea (2.0 million ha), cassava (2.0 million ha) and yam (2.0 million ha). According to Thisday Newspaper (2016), the Ebonyi State Government Rice Project produced 190,000 tonnes of rice across the state.

The achievement was also facilitated by the IFAD and FADAMA III project which played a welcome role by assisting the farmers to put 6,000 hectares and 2,000 hectares of land, respectively, into rice cultivation in the 2016 wet season. Meanwhile, the state government launched a one-man, one-hectare scheme in its determined effort to make the state Nigeria's number one rice producer during his allocation of lands to commissioners and others for compulsory rice production. The Ebonyi State government led by Governor David Nweze Umahi also enlightened the public that his administration was determined to empower over 1,000 youths and 1,000 women to go into agriculture and other semi-skilled business that would take off with soft loans.

United Nation refers to youth as persons within the age bracket of 15 and 25 years without prejudice to other member state definition, while United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization refers to youth in African Youth Charter as persons within the age bracket of 15 and 35 years (<http://www.unesco.org>). According to National Youth Policy (2009), youth in Nigeria is person within the age bracket of 18 and 35 years. Moreover, in present Nigeria as reported in Vision 2020 report, 60% of the population constitutes the youths; the youths have made significant impact on the national development over the years (Adekunle *et al.* (2009). In contrast, in the rural areas of southern Nigeria, youth’s involvement in agricultural production is on the decrease. This is why Russel reported in Adekunle *et al.* (2009) that despite the fast growing opportunities in agricultural sector, it is alarming and quite incredible to see many rural youths opting out of farming in search of non-existent white-collar jobs in the cities, leading to unprecedented level of rural-urban migration.

Some of the constraints that face youth involvement in rice production in Nigeria include: poor capital base, use of archaic implements, lack of extension contacts, incidence of pests and diseases, lack of improved inputs and bad attitude to farming (Onuk *et al.*, 2010). In the view of gender inequality, youths male and female status are very low, they are overwhelmingly more disadvantaged than adult male, and face continuous discrimination. According to Gender Assessment Report in 2015, these inequalities are not only a threat to youth farmers’ basic human rights, but also pose a serious threat to the social and economic development of youth farmers’ (Ellna, n.d).

Therefore, the focus of this study is to examine the effect of socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers on the rice production project in Ishielu local government area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- (i) Ascertain the socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers that are involved in the rice production project.
- (ii) Analyze the extent of youth farmers’ participation in Ebonyi State rice production.
- (iii) Determine the effect of the socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers on the rice production activities performed in the study area.

The null hypothesis tested;

- (i) The extent of participation in the rice production project is independent on the socio-economic characteristics of youth farmers in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Ishielu Local Government

area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The area is located between latitude 6° 25' 37" N of equator and longitude 7° 50' 9" E of Greenwich meridian (<http://www.geonames.org/search.html?q=Ebonyi,%20Nigeria>), and the headquarter located in Ezzillo town. It has a land area of 872 km² and population of 152,581 people in 2006, comprising of 72,671 males and 79,910 females (National Bureau of Statistics, 2011). The area has four development centers as thus: Ishielu, Ishielu East, Ishielu North and Ishielu West with twelve communities, namely: Umuhuali, Ntezi, Amazu, Ezillo, Okpoto, Nkalagu, Ezzagu, Lyonu, Obeagu, Agba, Azuinyaba, and Nkalaha, and 16 council wards. The major crops cultivated in the area include: maize, rice yam, cassava, cocoyam, potatoes, groundnut, and vegetables (<http://www.nigeria.gov.ng/index.php/2016-04-06-08-39-54/south-east/ebonyi-state>).

Based on the nature of the research, the study adopted a cluster purposive sampling techniques in order to ensure that the targeted respondents were purposively selected which guarantees access to the needed data. The respondents were met on their days of meeting at the local government headquarter where 10 respondents from the 12 communities that made up the local government area were randomly selected to give a total of 120 respondents. Data were collected from the respondents using a close-ended questionnaire. Descriptive statistics (frequency, mean and percentage distribution) were used to realize objective i, data collected for objective ii was analysed using mean score analysis while inferential statistics such as ordinal logit regression analysis using maximum likelihood procedure was used to achieve objective iii. Also, the null hypothesis was tested with chi-square statistics.

Model specification: The model for mean score analysis is specified thus:

$$X_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n X_j N_j}{N_r} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where

- Xi = Mean score
- Σ = Summation
- Xj = Likert value
- Nj = Number of respondents that choose that Likert value (Frequency that selected the same Likert value)
- Nr = Total Number of respondents.

Decision rule: Accept for mean score >2.5 otherwise reject; for four point Likert Scale Rating. The analytical tool has been applied by Mgbanya *et al.*, (2019).

The ordinal regression model with logit link function shows the nature of the deterministic relationship between an ordinal explained variables and continuous or dummy or nominal explanatory variables or stochastic

term. The technique produces the estimates and estimates standard error of logit regression, Wald test, Pseudo R², model fitting information Chi-square and Chi-square statistics for; the goodness of fit of the model and the test of parallel line. The model is specified as:

$$Y_i = F(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n) \dots \dots \dots \text{Implicit form} \dots \dots \dots 2$$

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_{11} X_{11} + e_t \dots \dots \dots \text{Explicit form} \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where:

Y_i = Project activities performed by the participating youth farmer (1= very low extent, 2=low extent, 3 = high extent, 4 = very high extent)

β_0 = Thresholds

$\beta_1 - \beta_{10}$ = Estimates

e_t = Sample error term

X_1 = Age (Years)

X_2 = Annual farm income before participating in the project (Naira)

X_3 = Annual farm income after participating in the project (Naira)

X_4 = Nonfarm Income (Naira)

X_5 = Farm size (Hectares)

X_6 = Household size (Number of persons)

X_7 = Marital status (0 = single or 1= married)

X_8 = Educational qualification (Number of years spent in school)

X_9 = Primary occupation (1 = farming, 2 = civil service, 3 = public service, 4 = trading)

X_{10} = Membership to cooperative (1 = yes, 0 = No)

The pseudo R² measures the relative amount of variation in the explained variables (Y_i) as accounted for by the included explanatory variables ($X_{(s)}$). Wald test measures the statistical significant effect of the estimate on the explained variables against the basis of null hypothesis value of zero (0). The model fitting information chi-square statistics tests if the model gives better prediction, the chi-square statistics for goodness of fit tests if the observed frequencies is significantly similar to the expected frequencies when more than two outcomes are possible, it also test if the observe data are consistent with the fitted model while the test of parallel lines chi-square test the dependence relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

The socio-economic characteristics examined were: age, marital status, household size, educational level, annual

farm revenue, non-farm income, farm size, primary occupation, and membership to social group. The results in (Table 1) indicated that the greater number of participants that were involved in the Ebonyi state government rice project is within the age bracket of 36 to 40 years. This implies that the group of farmers who were above youth age was involved in the project at a greater percentage. The result also indicates that about 43.3 % of the farmers involved in the project were youth. According to Nwibo *et al.* (2016) as reported by Food and Agricultural Organization, the result is consistent with the active age of agricultural labour force which is between 31-40 years. Consciously or unconsciously, the project adopted this active age of agricultural labour force propounded by Food and Agricultural Organization during their selection. From the result of the data analysis, most of the participants (65.8%) were male. Due to the fact that rice production in a crude form involves tedious activities, stronger gender such as male are needed more than the female counterpart who are regarded as weaker vessel. In addition, ownership of land is always ascribed to the male counterparts. This result is in line with Nwibo *et al.* (2016) who reported that most of the agripreneurs (64.20%) in Ishielu local government area of Ebonyi state were male.

However, 78.3% of the participants in the project were married with a mean household size of 7 and mean farm size of 2.8 hectares. The mean farm size of 2.8 ha indicates that apart from the one man one hectare of land advocated by the project, the participants also farm their left over farms in order to obtain average total revenue of about 1,048, 330 naira. This is consistent with Adebowale (2016); report on Governor David Umahi speech; “how we grew rice production in Ebonyi state to 190,000 metric tonnes this year” that each farmer cultivated between 2-3 hectares of land out of more than 30,000 hectares across the local government areas in the state. The result of the data analysis further shows that 71.7 % of the participants attended tertiary education. This shows that the project helped in reducing the rate of unemployment among graduates in the study area. Meanwhile, the primary occupation (72.5%) of the participants is farming while 100 % of the participants are member of social groups in their communities. This might be as a result of the participants through their educational exposure had known that most development programmes are usually first brought to the social groups found in the community through their leaders.

The extent of youth farmers’ participation in the rice production

The result in (Table 2) shows the information about the extent of youth farmers’ participation in Ebonyi State Rice Production Project in Ishielu Local Government Area. The result showed that the activities that youth farmers participate in the Ebonyi State rice project were in

Table 1. Percentage Distribution on the Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents.

Socio-economic	Frequency (n=120)	%	Mean
Age			
<30	9	7.5	
31 – 35	43	35.8	
36- 40	56	46.7	36
>40	12	10	
Sex			
Male	79	65.8	
Female	41	34.2	
Marital status			
Single	26	21.7	
Married	94	78.3	
Educational qualification			
Primary Education	17	14.2	
Secondary Education	17	14.2	
Tertiary Education	86	71.7	
Annual farm revenue (₦)			
<500,000	26	21.71	1,048,330
500,000 – 900,000	33	27.5	
900,000 – 1,300,000	9	7.5	
1,300,000 – 1,700,000	43	35.8	
>1,700,000	9	7.5	
Household size			
<4	17	14.2	7
4-7	42	35	
8-11	35	29.2	
>11	26	21.7	
Farm size (ha)			
<2	18	15	2.8
2-3	69	57.5	
3-4	33	27.5	
Primary occupation			
Farming	87	72.5	
Civil service	8	6.7	
Public Service	8	6.7	
Trading	17	14.2	
Membership of social organization			
Yes	120	100	
No	0	0	

Source: Field Survey, 2018

stakeholders meeting/decision making (3.3417), site selection (3.2750), land clearing (2.7750), making of beds/ridge with hoes (2.6250), making of beds/ridges with tractor (2.8000), manual direct seed planting (2.8500), manual seed broadcasting (3.1833), manual transplanting (2.7250), manual weeding (2.9833), chemical application with knapsack (2.8000), harvesting with sickles (2.7083), transportation of the rice from the farm to the storage (3.0583), manual threshing (3.3417), manual winnowing (2.6333), manual bagging (3.2667) and marketing of the rice to the government buyers (2.5500) were accepted. This implies that most of the activities partake by the youth farmers in the project were manual ways of farming which uses man power and brings about low productivity. The only form of

mechanization that is greatly employed in the rice production is the use of tractor in making beds/ridges. This is in agreement with Food and Agricultural Organization observation as cited in Effiong *et al.* (2015) that in almost all rice growing areas in Nigeria, men traditionally undertake such activities as land preparation, ploughing, irrigation and field-leveling. This shows that the youth farmers do not engage more in mechanized system of rice farming in the area.

Effect of the socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers on the rice project activities

Ordinal regression analysis with logit link function was

Table 2. Mean score analysis on the extent of youth farmers' participation in Ebonyi State rice project.

Rice Production Activities	Mean (2.5)	Decision
Stakeholders meeting/decision making	3.3417	Accepted
Site selection	3.2750	Accepted
Land Clearing	2.7750	Accepted
Making of beds/ridges with hoe	2.6250	Accepted
Making of beds or ridges with tractor	2.8000	Accepted
Manual direct seed planting	2.8500	Accepted
Manual seed broadcasting	3.1833	Accepted
Manual transplanting	2.7250	Accepted
Use of planter	1.1500	Rejected
Use of trans-planter	1.3000	Rejected
Manual Weeding	2.9833	Accepted
chemical application with knapsack	2.8000	Accepted
chemical application with boom sprayer	1.8500	Rejected
Harvesting with sickles	2.7083	Accepted
Use of combine harvester	1.3000	Rejected
Transportation of the rice from the farm to the storage	3.0583	Accepted
Manual threshing	3.3417	Accepted
use of thresher	1.5000	Rejected
Manual winnowing	2.6333	Accepted
Use of winnower	1.6333	Rejected
Manual Bagging	3.2667	Accepted
Marketing of rice to the government buyers	2.5500	Accepted

Table 3. Ordinal regression analysis of the effect of the socio-economic characteristics of youth farmers on the rice project activities performed.

Variables	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald-Test
Age	0.561	0.168	11.129***
Annual farm income before	2.639E-006	8.953E-006	0.087 ^{NS}
Annual farm income after	8.428E-006	1.197E-005	0.495 ^{NS}
Non-farm income	-2.820E-005	4.830E-006	34.079***
Farm size	-0.229	0.526	0.189 ^{NS}
Household size	0.288	0.164	3.081**
Marital status=Single	-5.458	1.660	10.814***
Marital status=Married	0 ^a	0	0 ^{NS}
Educational qualifications=Primary	-3.361	0.762	19.461***
Educational qualifications=Secondary	-30.781	3.795	65.771***
Educational qualifications=Tertiary	0 ^a	.	. ^{NS}
Primary occupation=Farming	-17.150	2.484	47.682***
Primary occupation=Civil service	-25.041	3.464	52.244***
Primary occupation=Public service	27.265	4.262	40.923***
Primary occupation=Trading	0 ^a	0	0
Membership to social group=Yes	0 ^a	0	0

Model fitting information for intercept only*final

Chi-square value 201.710***

Pearson Chi-square value 2687.056***

Pseudo R2

Cox and Snell 0.814)

Nagelkerke 0.822)

McFadden 0.364)

Source: Field Survey, 2018

*** P level = 99% (0.01), ** P level = 95% (0.05), NS = Not significant, a = redundant parameter

employed to bring out the effects of the socio-economic characteristics of the participants on their extent of participation in Ebonyi State rice production project activities in the study area. The socioeconomic characteristics that were regressed against by the regressand were; age, marital status, household size,

educational qualifications, annual farm income before participating in the project, annual farm income after participating in the project, nonfarm income, farm size, primary occupation and membership to social group. The result of the data analysis is presented in (Table 3). The result showed that the coefficient of age has a positive

Table 4. Chi-square test of hypothesis that the extent of participation in the rice project activities is independent on the socio-economic characteristics of the participants in the study area.

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	352.902			
General	.000 ^b	352.902	108.000	

Source: Field Survey, 2018

effect with the project activities performed by the participating youth farmers at P -value = 0.01 level. This implies that those that their age falls within the youthful age and above participate at greater extent in the project activities. Hence, increase in age of the participating youth farmers lead to increase in the number of activities they performed. Annual farm income before and after participating in the project has no effect on the activities performed by the participants due to their non-significant effect. The result shows that non-farm income have a negative effect on the activities performed by the participating youth farmers at P -value = 0.01 level. This implies that decrease in the income earned from non-farming activities leads to increase in the number of activities performed by the participating youth farmers. Hence, the youth farmers of that area use farming activities to support low income that comes from non-farming activities such as civil and public services. The farm size of the participants has no effect on the activities they perform due to its non-significant nature. This indicates that the size of farms owned by participants is not a criterion for determining the extent of participating in the Ebonyi State rice project at the study area. The coefficient of household size was also positively significant at P -value = 0.05 level. This implies that increase in the household size leads to increase in the extent of the activities performed by the participants. This concur with Nwibo *et al.* (2016) that reported that household size was positively significant at $P=0.05$ level when they studied the effect of socio-economic attributes on rural households in becoming agripreneurs. In addition, increase in household size is an indication of family labour use in meeting the labour demand for rice production which has many activities. The result further shows that those that their marital status is single was negatively significant at P -value = 0.01 level. This shows that single youth farmers that participate in the project activities were less in number compared to married participants and yet they participate at greater extent in the project activities. Hence, single youth farmers were allowed to participate to a greater extent in the rice project activities. The result also shows that those that have primary and secondary educational qualification were negatively significant at P -value = 0.01 level. This means that participants with primary and secondary

educational qualification are less in number and they participate to greater extent in the rice project activities. It is pertinent to know that most activities of the rice project were done manually and this might be the reason why those with tertiary educational qualification were not significantly participating in the rice project activities at the study area. The result however shows that primary occupation such as farming and civil services estimates were negatively significant whereas public services estimate was positively significant at P -value = 0.01 level. This implies that those that their primary occupation are farming and civil services, have inverse relationship with the extent to which they participate in the project activities whereas those that their primary occupation is public service, has a direct relationship with the extent to which they participate in the project activities. Hence if the number of participating youths that were farmers and civil servants decreases, the extent to which they participate in the project activities increases whereas if the number of participating youths that are public servants increases, the extent to which they participate in the project activities increases. Also the model fitting information for intercept only and final chi-square value (201.710***) indicates that the model gives better prediction. However, the number of categorical predictor (factor) are small and there are no empty cells arising from the use of covariate variables in predicting the model, therefore the Pearson chi-square value (2687.056***) follows the chi-square distribution and the significance value is accurate. This implies that the observe data is consistent with the fitness of the model. The Nagelkerke value (0.822) is the adjusted pseudo R^2 version of Cox and Snell which indicates that an about 82% variation in the dependent variable is explained by the included categorical and covariate variables of the model. Therefore, from the Wald test result, the covariate and categorical variables that have a significant effect on the dependent variable were; age, non-farm income, household size, marital status (single), educational qualification (primary and secondary) and primary occupation (farming, civil and public services).

The result in (Table 4) shows that the chi-square statistics (352.902) is significant at 1% level of significance. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that the extent of participation in the rice project

activities is independent on the socio-economic characteristics of youth farmers in the study area is rejected. Hence, the extent of participation in the rice project activities is dependent on the socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers in the study area.

Conclusion and recommendations

In conclusion, the effects of socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers on the rice production project are significant in view of the existing dependent relationship among them. However, in order to stem the low involvement of single youths, age bracket inequality, and negative participation of the graduates in the project activities, the government should provide equal quota for the entire age bracket, gender and all level of education. Also government should employ the use of improved technology such as machines and machineries for the rice production project activities in the study area. This will encourage the young age youths and graduates to actively participate in the project.

Authors' declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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